

An Interactive Design Concept for Sustainability of Terracotta Production

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Abstract: Evolving technologies are the center of an ever-modernizing society and assisted by products of skills and labour. A lot of explorations and initiatives have been already taken by the concerned authorities for proper recognition of the craft form in the country. Lately, with the change in market trends and shortcomings of artisans the culture tends to decay with the passage of time. The fear of unemployment and various other obstacles have let the artisans with a doubt whether to pass it to the future generations. This paper aims to regain the past glory of Terracotta Industry through an interactive service design platform. Based on the inputs with the artisans of Assam, India, the current state of the market and capital was tallied through a questionnaire-based survey. The platform would essentially deal with the aspects of growth and progress of the artisans of Terracotta while providing newer opportunities at a global level. The advantageous aspects and challenges of implementing the design approach was firmly evaluated through user perceptions. In-depth investigation of the subject matter was done with proper utilization and implementation of the proposed aspect. The study also ventures through the economic uplifting of the artisans of the locality to have a better approach towards their recognition.

Practical Implications: The possible future scope of the module caters towards generating enhanced usability and experience in the arts and craft domain through modern and interactive platforms. This proposal tends to comprehend the actual user needs on the subject and validate the flexibility and feasibility of the proposed service design.

Keywords: Interaction; Interactive platform; Service Design; Terracotta; User Perception

1. Introduction and Background of Research

Terracotta, or red clay pottery, is one of the older ideas that man developed at the start of civilization. Pre-civilized men gave up their nomadic lifestyle, and for a very long time they lacked any knowledge of cooking or storage pots or vessels. Then again, some types of clay pots or vessels must have been urgently needed by intelligent brains to address due to the clay's abundance and ease of use, they have a storage and cooking issue (Mishra & Mansuri, 2016). India is home to the Kumbhar caste, and almost every village will have a settlement or community of potters. Based on the type of pottery they produce and the type of labour they offer, potters are further divided into groups (Bhattacharyya, 2014). They produce a variety of items, including fun toys and items for celebrations like festivals and births, as well as practical, votive, decorative, and religious items, deaths, marriages, and large terracotta statues used as votive offerings. Consequently, they have extremely versatile skills. Clay characteristics differ across the subcontinent as well (Mishra & Mansuri, 2016; Kasemi, 2014).

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Sustainability of Terracotta Production

Terracotta pottery is now held in the highest regard, so using these exquisite works of art as home decor is a real accomplishment. Terracotta pottery was first sculpted and made between 2600 and 1700 BC. Around that time, the Indus Valley Civilization flourished. While conducting excavations at Harappa and Mohenjo-Daro, archaeologists and historians discovered a variety of terracotta pots and vessels. You've probably guessed by now that only the most accomplished artisans are capable of mastering the art of creating terracotta pottery. Each piece of terracotta art or sculpture is crafted with the utmost skill and elegance. Terracotta pottery is prized so highly and costs so much because each piece requires a lot of time and patience (Kumar, 2021). The Indus Civilization saw the art develop and advance thanks to technology, and today both small and large pottery companies consider it to be a significant cottage industry (Siddiqui, 2018).

The terracotta army was created in honour of Qin Shi Huang, the first emperor of the Qin dynasty, who ruled over China in 2133. When Qin passed away in 246 BC, according to the records of great historians, he gave Qin Shi Huang the order to start building the mausoleum. He assumed control of Qinzhou. The terracotta army's purpose was to "protect" the entire mausoleum, and Qin Shi Huang thought that the army would also be able to shield him from harm in the afterlife (Song, 2023).

One of the earliest examples of human creativity is the ancient art form of terracotta. For centuries, it has been a crucial component of every Indian home. His experience is rooted in long-standing traditions that go back to the days of our family. Due to the fact that it combines four of the five essential elements—air, earth, fire, and water—it is traditionally thought of as a mysterious substance. This genuine form of art eventually came to an end. Terracotta pottery almost vanished from the market during the era of technological advancement (Roy & Bhardwaj, 2021).

Terracotta is still practiced in Indian society and daily life, making it an ethnic manifestation of Indian culture in and of itself. Every village in India has Kumbhar members (potter caste). Pottery is significant in a rural country with low financial resources and few requirements. The clay is cleansed and filtered before being blended with sand to form a dough. As the wheel revolves, the artist molds the clay with their hands. The chakra (potter's wheel) is the most used equipment for making terracotta. Other tools used to embellish the pots include iron and bamboo sticks. The necessary thickness is achieved by baking with hay and coconut husks. It is then baked at temperatures ranging from 600 to 1000 degrees Celsius, which helps to reinforce the clay (Fredrick, 2023).

Due to the rising demand for home décor items, nations like India, China, Philippines, Thailand, Singapore, and Malaysia are some of the main consumers of many different types of earthenware. From middle-class consumers who are wealthy in these nations. The steady economic growth anticipated in many developed and developing countries is a supporter of the market growth for clay and refractory products. According to IMF predictions, the global GDP will be 3.3% in 2020 and 3.4% in 2021.

In India, almost all households use pottery-derived goods. These include water containers, earthen pots for plants and flowers, and exquisitely crafted lamps or diyas in a variety of sizes and shapes to brighten their home. During the holiday season, demand for these items increases even more. For instance, during the Diwali festival, Hindus decorate their homes with a variety of diyas and lights to make them beautiful and shining. Just before the Dussehra festival, which was widely celebrated across the nation with great fanfare, there was a huge demand for simple yet lovely clay toys. Additionally, the Kalash or pot is also frequently bought during the wedding season. West Bengal is renowned for having a long history of terracotta art. In fact, this is where some of the temple's terracotta panel designs with the most exquisite details are created. Hooghly, Murshidabad, Digha, and Jessore are a few of the Bengali towns most well-known for their terracotta artwork. The Bankura horse is another well-known term connected to West Bengali terracotta art. It is a sizable red clay horse with exquisite decorations. The Madhya Pradesh region of Bastar is well known for its terracotta pottery tradition and rich culture. The Bastar tribes produce exquisite artwork, detailed statues of horses, elephants, and birds, as well as stunning traditional clay temples (Earthenware Market, 2023).

Additionally, sacrifices were offered to the deity using the statues. Gujarat is renowned for its exquisite hand-painted wheel-made clay products. The most well-liked of these are clay pots that have been expertly crafted and embellished with striking geometric patterns, fish shapes, and more. The Aiyandar sect produced the most popular type of earthenware in Tamil Nadu. Large, lifelike statues of elephants and horses are among the well-known terracotta figurines that they produce. The state of Haryana is well known for its distinctive and wildly popular clay wares. These include customary hukkah items like smoking pipes and vases as well as more commonplace items like teapots, mugs, water pots, wall lamps, spotlights, and lovely animal figurines (Earthenware Market, 2023).

Earthenware pottery used in domestic settings is traditionally made by the Orissan tribes. Terracotta tea cups, pots, kitchenware, and other common yet practical items are just a few of what they produce. Horses, elephants, and other animals with realistic-looking figures are also produced. A village in the Dhuburi district called Asharikandi. The area is well-known for its exquisite pottery and terracotta artwork. Clay dolls and toys, mythical figures, terracotta vases and pots, and other items are some of the most well-liked terracotta goods in Assam (Earthenware Market, 2023).

The main sales segment of these craftsmen can be classified by the type and location of the customer:

- International retail customers
- International organizations
- National organization
- Domestic individual

Out of the four listed above, it is clear which segment brings in the most money and makes the most profit for the company. It's interesting to note how little domestic individual consumers are taken advantage of in certain situations, including craft fairs, online marketing through social networks, word-of-mouth, e-commerce websites, etc. Many aggregators don't make much of an effort to reach out to domestic customers because the international customer segment is always given priority (Tripathi, 2021).

The owner is the craftsman, who employs himself and uses his own resources and initiative. Currently, 70% of potters travel no more than 10 km to bring clay for red clay pottery, and there are some locations where one must travel more than 75 km to get the proper clay, which raises the transportation cost. Only 27% of respondents fall into the monthly income group of Rs 5000 or less, 40% are from the Rs 5000–10,000 income group, 32% are from the Rs 10000–20,000 income group, and 40% are from the Rs 5000–10,000 income group. It is significant on its own. Percentages are used because it is currently impossible for any family to meet all of this amount's daily requirements. Due to the inability of Indian red clay (terracotta) pottery workshops to pay their workers a living wage and construct separate huts for their production, 90% of potters are classified as living below the poverty line (Gangopadhyay & Sen, 2019 ;Yadav et al., 2022).

The product market is mainly regional and touches some urban areas. Additionally, brokers are crucial in the sale of these locally produced goods. Typically, they place orders with artisans and purchase materials for less than what the market will bear. Competition with substitutes, like plastic products, is a significant obstacle to its development. A variety of socioeconomic issues plague craftsmen in Panchmura, West Bengal, and they continue to lag behind other communities. They are primarily harmed by advancements in technology and economic resources. The village's artisans are in a poor financial situation. They primarily produce using methods from long ago (Lakshman, 1966).

93% of respondents to a survey in Majuli, Assam, stated that they stopped making pottery for 3-5 months during the flood season because they lacked a suitable workspace. None of the survey participants wanted their kids to learn this long-standing tradition occupation (Regon, 2019).

The geographic scope of a low-level artisan's target markets and clientele is limited. Therefore, it should be possible for an online market to gain more exposure. In the current era of technology and advertising, an internet marketing strategy may attract both domestic and foreign customers. As a result of this development, they can learn about modern trends and western expectations. Outside of government programmers and workshops, the government did not actively contribute to the development of terracotta, so this might also catch their attention. Etsy, Amazon Karigar, AuthIndia, Craftsvilla, and other sites and apps that are currently in use include these. These programmes and websites each have a different method and strategy for promoting terracotta products and other crafts as well as the artists who make them (Browntape, 2015)

Through an interactive service design platform, the goal of this paper is to restore the former glory of the terracotta industry. A questionnaire-based survey was used to determine the market and capital conditions based on input from Assam, India, artisans. The platform would primarily focus on the development and growth of Terracotta artisans while also presenting fresher opportunities on a global scale. Through user perceptions, the benefits and difficulties of putting the design approach into practice were thoroughly assessed. A thorough investigation of the subject was conducted while correctly leveraging and putting the suggested aspect into exercise. The study also tries to improve the economic standing of the local artisans in order to better understand how to approach their recognition.

2. Design Process

Figure 1. Follow Diagram of Design Process & Methods.

3. Methodology

The financial aspect was considered because it was necessary for the artisans to have a platform where their area of interest and source of income are combined with an interactive approach. Most terracotta artisans are somewhat accustomed to using technological devices, particularly smartphones and tablets, so in order to reach as many users as possible, the content must be made available through these channels. All these important considerations went into the decision to use an interactive platform as the design strategy.

Understanding the user's genuine wants and the obstacles provided by the existing circumstance while seeking to handle the issue at hand was critical before implementing the design strategy. Since customers are a crucial component of the aspect, it was crucial to find out what they thought of the strategy. The incorporation of possible digital aspects was also considered because excellent user engagement is another crucial criterion for having a big user base and might be handled through an immersive experience.

The research was separated into two stages: the first featured a detailed survey about consumers' opinions and wants, and the second involved a prototype and discussion survey with students studying design in collaboration with academic professors and teachers. Professionals from the industry inspected the prototype and gave input, which was subsequently considered.

3.1. Phase 1

The first element of the research looks on the existing state of digital content exposure on Terracotta and Terracotta artists. Exposure of digital content refers to the coverage of skills and availability of a platform to showcase the skills in digital medium for the artisans in which they could indulge and could make a living. This was mainly done to have a proper understanding of the expertise of the artisans in using digital driven solutions for their products and skills. Scenarios were created based on existing literature and initial interactions with the artisans of Terracotta. The modes of awareness and for the artisans along with the proper guidance for education were also explored. The reason for this was to understand the opportunities available for cognitive impartment of skills for future generations of artisans, so that the tradition of making Terracotta could carry on with the newer generations. The economical factor was also a crucial aspect to upheld during the study as it would be the main income source of the artisans by selling their products. Available platforms to offer that were reviewed thoroughly and the opportunities were analyzed accordingly. Competitive analysis and SWOT analysis based on the inputs were carried out for the present market scenario to have a firm understanding of the situation and opportunities for the artisans. After exploring the facets of Terracotta, a suggestion for an alternative method was made to artisans in the area, who could respond with solutions for how the suggestion could be improved for a suitable user base. After recording all relevant replies from the design process, a questionnaire-based survey was employed. With the help of an eleven-question survey, a total of hundred people in Kokrajhar, Assam, India, participated in the survey. Among the respondents there were artisans, design students, professors and people who came across the stated issue in hand. The questionnaire is provided to users in the form of links in Google Forms, allowing them to participate from the comfort of their own homes.

As mentioned, the questionnaire had ten questions regarding the current state of Terracotta and the artisans and to enquire about the actual need for an alternative interactive digital platform so that more opportunities based on skill and income could be provided to them for upholding the tradition.

Question 1, talks about the current situation of Terracotta and the household culture associated with it. It investigates the tradition's deteriorating trajectory, and respondents were invited to provide their opinions about it. Question 2 explores the market scenario of Terracotta and opportunities associated with it and exemplified. Participants were asked to share their thoughts about it. Question 3, talks about the pricings of Terracotta sculptures that the artisans receive. It explores the justified extents of price that the artisans receive for their skills and the respondents were asked to state their thoughts. Question 4 explores the region-specific opportunities available for the artisans and the respondents were asked to respond according to their regional demography. Question 5 discusses the availability of raw materials for artists as well as the obstacles they confront when transporting them. The respondents were asked to state their thoughts. Question 6 deals with the natural calamities, particularly in Assam and how they have been affecting the businesses of the Terracotta artisans. The respondents' views were sought. Question 7 asks about client demand during non-festive seasons and what viable solutions the answers have for this issue. Question 8 speaks about the role of the government in providing opportunities to the artisans for flourishing their business. The respondents were invited to express their opinions. Question 9 speaks about the exposure and recognition based on their work. Question 10 deals with the proposal of an interactive platform that would essentially provide with more exposure, assured prices and tracking the market scenario for the artisans. It was to provide them with better opportunities.

3.2. Phase 2

The second part of the study devoted on the genuine dissertation of user needs based on the results of the quantitative survey of users. The plan was devised to adequately handle the craftsmen and their facilities in order to preserve the family tradition. The aspects of interactivity and engagement was prominently taken into consideration, as these would essentially contribute to the use of an interactive digital platform for their skilled products. The idea was to promote their works in form of an innovative e-commerce platform that would deal with buying and selling of Terracotta products. This would lead to a greater opportunity for the artisans to continue their skilled works while also encouraging young minds to take up the occupation. They would also find a platform to earn their daily living while also providing a definite identity to them. Post the phase of identifying the needs of the users, the actual formation of the platform was done. The look and feel of the interactive platform were designed according to the above-mentioned needs for the users considering both the artisans and the potential buyers of the Terracotta items. The aesthetical aspects along with the visual prominence of the platform was given utmost importance. The elements were kept simple as many artisans were moderately able to handle digital content and so the navigation too was kept minimalistic. An approach was made to spread the awareness about the platform among the normal masses and artisans so that they would get to know about the existence and working of the platform.

The inclusion of personas was done to get a clear visual of what is the necessary need and the demand which need to be fulfilled in this project. This also points out the goals and the frustrations of the user that they face from following the normal process. Hence, making it comfortable for us to understand the gap that needs to be fulfilled through the product.

3.2.1. User Journey Mapping

In this process, we had inspected the process user uses to do to perform a certain objective. Here we can see the journey an artisan and a buyer follow to accomplish their certain goals. This also projects the pain points that are going to be useful in the idea generation phase. The emotion graph shown in the user journey map describes the user mentality which is useful for better understanding of the user.

[A]

[B]

Figure 2. [A][B] User Journey Mapping of both sellers and buyers.

3.2.2 Existing User Flow

The existing user flow shows the usual process followed by the user to complete the task. It provides a detail information about the path they follow and the hassle they face. Providing a glimpse about what to solve and how to do it to minimize the hassle.

[A]

[B]

Figure 3. [A][B] Existing User Flow that the artisans and buyers follow

3.2.3. Empathy Mapping

In this process, based on the previous data found we found out about the emotional status of the users. The emotional and the physical behaviour the user showcases while performing the desired actions. In this user empathy map we found out that the problems faced by the artisans in selling the products and the change in their behaviour prior to what they think or say. Whereas, for the customer the lengthy procedure they follow along with the change in their mindset while performing the task. It also displays the common problems both the party faces which can be avoided with the existence of an interactive platform.

[A]

Figure 4. [A][B] Empathy mapping for both artisans and customers.

3.2.4. Problems and Features

This is the cart sorting process, which is done based on all the information found on the prior research and the problems found from it. Using this brainstorming process, we found out the features and solutions that should be incorporated in the interactive platform to minimize the difficulties faced by the artisans and the customers.

[A]

[B]

Figure 5. [A][B] Idea generating of features based on the problems.

3.2.5. Updated User Flow

The updated user flow provides a wider prospective on how this platform can reduce the hassle and provide a simple path for the users. This simpler path attracts user and the interactive features provides them with a wider possibility.

[A]

[B]

Figure 6. [A][B] Updated User Flow if the app acts as a bridge.

3.2.6. Information Architecture

In this Information Architecture, we had shown the buttons and the screens that are present in the application. It also shows the varieties present in the application for the user to perform. The artisans one shows a simplified approach, so that even an artisan with low education and technological enlightenment can use it whereas, for the consumers there are features and screens only for their preferences and demands to help the complete their task easily and effectively, whilst saving time.

[A]

[B]

Figure 7. [A][B] Information Architecture of the Interactive platform for consumers and artisans respectively.

3.2.7. Navigation Flow

In this navigation flow, we showed the skeleton of the application and how it would operate and function. This provides a vision about the result that we are expecting.

[A]

[B]

Figure 8. [A] and [B] Navigation Flow of the interactive platform.

3.2.8. Low-Fidelity

In this low fidelity, we focused how the platform would look and how it should layout the UI without any colour to provide how it need to be presented.

This colour scheme, typography was selected to give the theme of terracotta and to provide a nostalgic interaction with the interface. It guided our vision to how the final MVP should be showcased to the user.

Figure 9. Low-fidelity Wireframes for the interactive platform.

3.2.9. High-Fidelity

This was the outcome of the UI how it would look. After quite an alteration of the design ideas, this minimalistic design was selected along with the various interactive icons. The insights section for the artisan's section helps the user to process transaction along with keeping a close eye on the incoming and outgoing money along with notifying them about the increase and decrease of sales for a certain product.

Figure 10. High Fidelity Screens of the platform.

3.2.10. Prototyping

After completing all the needed phases of the second part of the research, it was time for the user discussion survey. The discussion survey was carried out with the use of an interactive platform prototype. It was desired to have a strong grasp on the practicality of the suggested design approach. Students with design backgrounds and local craftspeople were also contacted since they could give useful insight on the user experience and its breadth in the proposal.

Figure 11. 1st MVP or prototype of the platform.

Figure 12. [A] [B] Interview and interacting the artisans.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Results of Phase-1

According to the results obtained through the survey conducted in Phase-1, Question 1 saw 30.5% of the respondents to agree with the fact, 55.2% of the respondents strongly agreed, 4.8% disagreed and 1% strongly disagreed. In Question 2, 20% of the respondents agreed with the fact, 46.7% strongly agreed, 14.3% disagreed and 8.6% strongly disagreed. Question 3 had 23.8% of the respondent to agree with the scenario presented, 49.5% strongly agreed, 7.6% disagreed and 10.5% strongly disagreed. In Question 4, 22.9% of the respondents agreed, 59% strongly agreed, 4.8% disagreed and 3.8% strongly disagreed. Question 5 saw 22.9% of the respondents to agree with the problem faced, 56.2% of the respondents strongly agreed, 3.8% disagreed and 1% strongly disagreed. According to the proposal put forward in Question 6, 23.8% of the respondents agreed, 64.8% strongly agreed, 1.9% disagreed and 1% strongly disagreed. Question 7 noticed 24.8% of the respondents to agree with the fact, 58.1% of the respondents strongly agreed, 3.8% disagreed and 1.9% strongly disagreed. In Question 8, 20% of the respondents agreed with the fact, 58.17% strongly agreed, 3.8% disagreed and 1.9% strongly disagreed. Question 9 had 21.9% of the respondent to agree with the scenario presented, 70.5% strongly agreed, 0% disagreed and 1% strongly disagreed. In Question 10, 28.6% of the respondents agreed, 61.9% strongly agreed, 1.9% disagreed and 1% strongly disagreed. The graph of the results obtained is depicted in Figure 13.

Through this procedure, one can gain a clear picture of public perceptions toward terracotta and the issues that artisans face. Questions 1 and 2 effectively illustrate people's insights regarding the current state of terracotta and market practices, as the results clearly implicate the poor condition faced by the craftsmen, as the participants clearly agree. The answers to

questions 3, 4, and 6 show that people recognize the issues that craftspeople face. More over half of those polled strongly concur. As a result, this poll clearly shows that the terracotta industry is deteriorating, and people are aware of it.

This poll serves as an eye-opener as to why this platform is critical for artists and the future of Indian terracotta. This platform clearly addresses the issues raised in Questions 3,4,5. This problem easily solves the cost and middleman difficulties, revealing it to be an appropriate answer to the problems faced by terracotta artisans in recent times.

Figure 13. Results obtained during Phase-1.

4.2. Results of Phase-2

An interactive session with other designers, users and artisans were done, to get a valid response on their take on this product prototype. Group discussions are done for varied ideas and feedbacks. The user testing was done with a total of 20 people, and 10 top responses are displayed in Table 1. The craftsmen who took part in the prototype survey were ecstatic with the concept. The other participants loved the UI and the development. The results were fairly encouraging, and the progress seemed to be in the correct direction.

The comments from the discussion survey were recorded in order to improve the concept. The feedback and response statistics are shown below in Table.1.

Figure 14. [A] [B] User Testing of the prototype with other designers.

Table 1. Feedback Table of the Discussion Survey.

Name	Profession	Feedbacks
Avishek Chakraborty	Government Employee	I like the idea and the execution. The colour scheme gives the feel of terracotta.I think it can really help the artisans in a better way
Suman Das	Salesman	The idea is great. But the interface need more works.I think more screens would give a proper view
Jahnabi Devi	Student	The interface needs more work.But I would still wants to see how it works out. The buyer section looks fine,the seller one needs more screens. Overall, I loved the approach.Will definately want to try once
Kaushik Dey	Civil Engineer	Need more features and will want to know about the marketing and advertising ideas.People are less aware of this kind of initiative.So the advertisement plays a major roll.
Souvik Sengupta	Designer	The features can't be used to the utmost possibility.The pictures clicked by the artisan won't have a better quality and they also don't have a proper sense of photography,so customer won't be attracted to buy that
Sandipan Bhattacharjee	Designer	The innovation is remarkable.There is more need of work done about the frames.Otherwise everything is ok.
Anurag.M	Developer	The Idea is good but the implementation should be tested
Angana Sudradhar	Designer	The idea is good along with the wireframes
Sudarshan Kalita	Designer	The interface needs more work and the features should be more expressing
Mrinmoy Deka	Designer	Good.I liked the interface and the idea. Would be happier to see the progress

From the feedbacks collected, it is evident that the idea in whole could be an innovative approach towards restoring. The bridge between artisans and the consumers were always weak and misleading. The idea of an interactive platform creates a room and a safe space for the artisans to come and share their products as a reasonable price. The UI design gives a feeling of terracotta which brings the essence of it, while the UX is made simple and interactive so that people can easily get the gist of it. Although, on the bright side, one can notice positive comments about this proposal, the users appear to be quite pleased with the initiative, lending support to the idea and the value it holds if developed and implemented properly.

5. Conclusion

This potential application aims to eliminate the bias treatment that artists encounter by serving as a platform for selling clay products from underestimated craftspeople to clients all over the world. Some common examples include middlemen, geographical disadvantages, less exposure, and even poor wages for their work. While resolving the deteriorating status of terracotta artists in India through a participatory design process, various major barriers such as a lack of markets, poor per-capita income, transportation issues, and so on might potentially be overcome.

The aforementioned analysis of the need and desire for a safe market for selling things might potentially be extremely valuable to them. With the government's support, this may be a powerful remedy to the deterioration of this art form.

This application implements a notion aimed at closing the gap between artists and customers. Because this application is currently in its prototype stage, it merely shows the fundamentals of the idea. This idea can be expanded upon with the correct initiative. Future plans may also include incorporating AI and various marketing ideas to aid in the fulfilment of its mission. This application can also be used as an extension for a large shopping site, engaging a niche audience and increasing the popularity, hence spreading awareness of the Indian terracotta industry as well as age-old artworks and designs.

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